

Personality Traits in Different Dental Speciality Students- A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) Is Widely Utilized In Health Professions Education To Understand Personality Diversity. It Categorizes Individuals Based On Four Dichotomies: Extraversion–Introversion (E–I), Sensing–Intuition (S–N), Thinking–Feeling (T–F), And Judging–Perceiving (J–P). Using The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator Questionnaire, The Study Aimed To Ascertain The Most Prevalent Personality Type Among Dentists In Dental Colleges Located In The East Coast Region Of Andhra Pradesh, Across Different Dentistry Specialties. Additionally, The Study Sought To Determine The Association Between Personality Types And Specialties. **Materials And Methods:** A Cross-Sectional Study Was Conducted Involving 200 Postgraduate Dental Students From Five Randomly Selected Dental Colleges In The East Coast Region Of Andhra Pradesh. Participants Completed A Two-Part Questionnaire: A Demographic Survey And The MBTI Assessment. Data Were Analyzed Using Descriptive Statistics And The Chi-Square Test Was Used To Determine Association Between Specialty And Personality Type. **Results:** The Most Prevalent Personality Type Among Study Participants Was ESFP (19%), Followed By INFP (11.5%) And ISFP (10%). Statistically Significant Associations Were Found Between Certain Personality Types And Dental Specialties ($P < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The Study Reveals A Significant Variation In Personality Types Among Different Dental Specialties, With ESFP (19%) Being The Most Common. Understanding These Personality Distributions Can Aid In Tailoring Educational Approaches And May Influence Career Guidance In Dental Education.

Keywords: Dental specialties, Myers-Briggs Type Indicator, Personality traits, Dental education, Career choice.

INTRODUCTION

Personality traits significantly influence individuals' behaviour, decision-making processes, and interpersonal interactions. In the context of dental education, understanding students' personality profiles can provide insights into their learning preferences, communication styles, and potential career paths. The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), developed by Isabel Briggs Myers and Katharine Cook Briggs, is a widely used psychometric tool that categorizes individuals into 16 personality types based on four dichotomous dimensions: Extraversion–Introversion (E–I),

Sensing–Intuition (S–N), Thinking–Feeling (T–F), and Judging–Perceiving (J–P) ^[1]. Despite debates regarding its reliability and validity ^[2], the MBTI remains popular in educational settings for fostering self-awareness and improving team dynamics ^[3]. Previous studies have explored the personality profiles of dental students and professionals. For instance, a systematic review by Li et al. highlighted prevalent MBTI types among dental students over five decades ^[4]. Other studies have examined the relationship between personality types and specialty choices in medicine and dentistry, suggesting that certain personality traits may align with specific specialties ^[5,6]. However, there is a paucity of research

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focusing on the personality profiles of postgraduate dental students in India, particularly concerning their chosen specialties. This study aims to fill this gap by identifying the prevalent MBTI personality types among postgraduate dental students in the east coast region of Andhra Pradesh, India, and examining the association between these personality types and their chosen dental specialties. Understanding these associations can inform educational strategies and career counseling in dental education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Participants:

A cross-sectional study was conducted over three months, involving postgraduate dental students from five randomly selected dental colleges of 13 colleges in the east coast region of Andhra Pradesh, India using simple random sampling technique. A sample size of 200 was determined using G power version 3.1

Data Collection:

Participants completed a two-part questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. The first part collected demographic information, including age, gender, specialty, and institution. The second part comprised the MBTI assessment, consisting of 20 items adapted from the official MBTI questionnaire [] validity of this questionnaire

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria encompassed all postgraduate dental students enrolled in the selected colleges. Faculty

members and undergraduate students were excluded from the study.

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (Pr.106/IEC/SIBAR/2022). Informed consent was secured from all participants.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic data and MBTI distributions. The Chi-Square test assessed associations between dental specialties and personality types, with a significance level set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Distribution Of Sample By Gender in Percentages

Among the 200 participants, 147 (73%) were female, and 53 (27%) were male.

Table 1: Distribution Of Study Subjects Based on Gender and Speciality

Speciality	Female	Male
public health dentistry	18	4
paediatric and preventive dentistry	16	6
orthodontics and dentofacial orthopaedics	15	7
periodontics and implantology	18	4
prosthodontics	16	6
oral pathology	20	3
oral and maxillofacial surgery	11	12
oral medicine and radiology	16	6
conservative dentistry and endodontics	17	5
Total	147	53

The distribution across dental specialties is detailed in Table 1. Notably, oral and maxillofacial surgery had a higher proportion of male students, while oral pathology had a higher proportion of female students.

Figure 2: Personality Types And Percentages

The distribution of personality types is illustrated in Figure 2. The most prevalent MBTI personality type was ESFP (19%), followed by INFP (11.5%) and ISFP (10%). Other notable types included ENFP and ISFJ (9% each), ENFJ (7.5%), and INFJ (6.5%), ENTP(6%), ESTP(5.5%), ESFJ(5%), INTP (4.5%), ISTJ, ESTJ(2%), ENTJ (1.5%), ISTP (1%).

Table 2: Distribution Of Study Participants in Specialities and Their Personality Types

SPECIALITY	DIFFERENT PERSONALITY TRIATS														
	ENFJ	INFP	ENTJ	ENTP	ESFJ	ESFP	ESTJ	ESTP	INFJ	INFP	INTP	ISFJ	ISFP	ISTJ	ISTP
Public health dentistry	4.5	18.2	4.5	4.5	0	31.8	0	0	0	13.6	4.5	0	18.2	0	0
Paediatric dentistry	9.1	9.1	9.1	9.1	13.6	13.6	0	9.1	9.1	0	0	0	0	9.1	9.1
Orthodontics	18.2	0	0	0	9.1	40.9	0	0	18.2	0	0	4.5	9.1	0	0
Periodontics	9.1	22.7	0	0	9.1	22.7	0	0	0	9.1	9.1	4.5	13.6	0	0
Prosthodontics	9.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	18.2	0	22.7	18.2	9.1	13.6	9.1	0
Oral pathology	0	13	0	4.3	0	4.3	8.7	0	0	17.4	8.7	30.4	13	0	0
Oral surgery	0	17.4	0	0	13	21.7	0	8.7	0	0	0	30.4	8.7	0	0
Oral medicine	0	0	0	22.7	0	22.7	0	13.6	0	27.3	0	0	13.6	0	0
Conservative dentistry	18.2	0	0	13.6	0	13.6	9.1	0	31.8	13.6	0	0	0	0	0

(E/I: Extrovert/Introvert, S/N: Sensing/Intuition, T/F: Thinking/Feeling, J/P: Judging/Perceiving)

Table 2 shows that ESFP is the most prevalent personality type among public health dentists, orthodontists, periodontists, and pedodontists. INFP is more commonly observed among prosthodontists and specialists in oral medicine and radiology, while INFJ is the dominant personality type among endodontists. ISFJ is more frequently found in oral and maxillofacial pathologists and oral surgeons. The association between personality type and dental specialty is highly statistically significant ($P = 0.000$).

DISCUSSION

From the perspective of person-centered personality psychology, understanding whether consistent personality configurations exist among dental professionals is a relevant and significant area of research. However, studies exploring the personality types of dental students and dentists have been relatively few and mostly limited to Western populations [5,6]. There is a notable lack of literature addressing personality traits among dental professionals in Middle Eastern and South Asian countries, highlighting the need for more region-specific research.

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) is one of the most widely used instruments for assessing personality traits [7,8]. It evaluates individuals across four dichotomies—Extraversion (E) vs. Introversion (I), Sensing (S) vs. Intuition (N), Thinking (T) vs. Feeling (F), and Judging (J) vs. Perceiving (P)—yielding 16 distinct personality types. In the current study, which involved postgraduate dental students from colleges along the east coast of Andhra Pradesh, 73% of participants were female and 27% were male. The most frequently reported personality types were ESFP (19%), INFP (11.5%), and ISFP (10%). ESFP individuals are often described as sociable, energetic, and adaptable, making them well-suited for the interactive and dynamic nature of dental practice. Extroverts, in particular, tend to excel in verbal communication and patient engagement, which are essential components of clinical dentistry. In this study, both male and female students showed a preference for Sensing (S) over Intuition (N), Feeling (F) over Thinking (T), and Perceiving (P) over Judging (J). These findings differ from those of Moris [6] and Yousef [5], who studied dental applicants in

the United Kingdom and reported dominant personality types such as ESFJ, ESTJ, ENFJ, and ENTJ—types associated with greater Judging and Thinking preferences.

When analyzed by specialty, ESFP emerged as the most common personality type among public health dentists, orthodontists, periodontists, and pedodontists. INFP was predominant among prosthodontists and specialists in oral medicine and radiology. INFJ was frequently found among endodontists, while ISFJ was more common among oral and maxillofacial pathologists and oral surgeons. The association between personality type and dental specialty was found to be highly statistically significant ($P = 0.000$), supporting similar observations reported in studies from other parts of the world [4,5,9]. Despite these valuable insights, one must consider the inherent limitations of using personality questionnaires like the MBTI. Human behavior and personality are highly complex and cannot be fully captured by a fixed set of categories. Individuals often do not conform rigidly to the typical traits assigned to their personality type, and situational, cultural, and developmental factors can influence how these traits are expressed [8].

CONCLUSION

The study identified ESFP and INFP as the most common personality types, both of which possess traits well-suited to the technical and specialized nature of dental work. ESFP was the most frequently observed across nine dental specialties, showing a strong correlation between personality profiles and specialty choice. These findings highlight the value of incorporating personality assessment into dental education and career guidance. Understanding personality traits may help align students with specialties where they are most likely to thrive. Further studies involving larger and more diverse groups are needed to confirm these results and explore their relevance to dental practice.

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REFERENCES

1. Myers IB, McCaulley MH, Quenk NL, Hammer AL. MBTI Manual: A Guide to the Development and Use of the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator. 3rd ed. Palo Alto (CA): Consulting Psychologists Press; 1998.
2. Pittenger DJ. Measuring the MBTI and coming up short. *J Career Plann Employ*. 1993;54(1):48–52.
3. Reilly JM, Trial J, Piver DE, Schaff PB. Myers-Briggs Type Indicator and its relationship to dental education and dental practice. *J Dent Educ*. 1983;47(7):450–5.
4. Li K, Nie Y, Li G, Lu Y. Personality traits of dental students: A systematic review. *J Dent Educ*. 2021;85(4):514–25.
5. Yousef A, Kassem H, Sahloul M, AlQarni M. Personality types and specialty preferences among dental students in Saudi Arabia. *BMC Med Educ*. 2020;20(1):47.
6. Moris IC, Fukuda CY, Vasconcelos BCE, Cury PR. Personality types and postgraduate dental specialty preferences: a study among Brazilian undergraduates. *J Dent Educ*. 2012;76(6):762–70.
7. Furnham A. The validity of the Myers–Briggs Type Indicator. *Curr Psychol*. 1996;15(3):225–38. .
8. Boyle GJ. Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI): Some psychometric limitations. *Aust Psychol*. 1995;30(1):71–4.
9. McCrae RR, Costa PT Jr. Validation of the five-factor model of personality across instruments and observers. *J Pers Soc Psychol*. 1987;52(1):81–90.

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